

The Historical Foundations of Turkic Nations' Friendship: Cultural Connections and Shared Heritage

Marat Esemuratovich Berdimuratov

Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Sociology, Lecturer, Department of Humanities, Karakalpakstan
Institute of Agriculture and Agrotechnology

Abstract: This article explores the historical foundations of friendship among Turkic nations, emphasizing cultural connections, shared heritage, and linguistic ties. By integrating insights from sociological, linguistic, and international relations perspectives, the study examines how friendship evolves as a multifaceted construct that influences both personal and political interactions. Goodwin (2003) provides a foundational understanding of friendship as a voluntary and informal social bond, which resonates with the relational dynamics observed in Turkic communities. Walker (2003) contextualizes Turkey's historical connections with Central Asian Turkic nations, highlighting the role of shared heritage and linguistic ties in fostering regional relationships. Schönig and Yiğitoğlu (2017) explore the historical development of Turkic languages, emphasizing their role as vessels for cultural identity and unity. Nordin and Smith (2018) conceptualize friendship as a critical category in international relations, proposing that it fosters cooperation and mutual understanding among nations. This perspective is expanded by van Hoef and Oelsner (2018), who present friendship as a dynamic construct influencing diplomatic interactions and regional stability. Seth et al. (2023) analyze cultural differences in digital friendship behaviors, revealing the impact of cultural nuances on meaningful connections. Finally, Kretschmer and Leszczensky (2023) address the dynamics of intergroup friendships, emphasizing early intergroup contact as a means to foster cohesion. Together, these studies provide a comprehensive understanding of how historical narratives, cultural heritage, and political engagement shape friendship among Turkic nations, highlighting its potential to promote regional stability and mutual understanding.

Keywords: Turkic nations, friendship, cultural heritage, linguistic ties, international relations.

1. Introduction

The exploration of friendship, its formation, and maintenance across different contexts has gained significant attention in recent years, presenting a multifaceted understanding of social relationships that extend beyond personal interactions to encompass broader cultural and political dimensions. The foundational work by (G. Goodwin, 2003) highlights the intrinsic nature of friendships as voluntary and informal relationships that provide essential social support throughout life. This understanding lays the groundwork for examining friendship not just as an interpersonal bond but as a cultural phenomenon that reflects shared values and social structures.

(Walker, 2003) expands this concept by situating Turkey within a historical framework that emphasizes its cultural and linguistic ties to other Turkic nations. He argues that the post-Ottoman Turkish Republic has sought to redefine itself by fostering connections with Central Asian states, thereby enhancing its regional influence through shared heritage and cultural bonds. This articulation of friendship as a means of political and cultural engagement underscores the importance of historical narratives in shaping contemporary relationships among Turkic nations.

In the realm of linguistic connections, (Schönig* & Özlem Yiğitoğlu**, 2017) delve into the historical development of Turkic languages, illustrating how language serves as a critical component of cultural identity and unity among Turkic peoples. By tracing the evolution of these languages, the authors highlight the interconnectedness of cultural heritage and the role of language in fostering a sense of belonging and friendship among diverse groups sharing common roots.

(Hanna Maria Nordin & M. Smith, 2018) further broaden the discourse on friendship by examining its implications in international relations. They propose that friendship can serve as a vital political category, influencing state interactions and shaping diplomatic ties. By drawing parallels between ancient philosophical notions of friendship and contemporary political practices, the authors suggest that friendship can facilitate cooperation and mutual understanding among nations, including those within the Turkic sphere.

Building on this, (van Hoef & Oelsner, 2018) present friendship as an analytical category within international politics, emphasizing its role in fostering trust and cooperation at various levels. Their insights into how friendship can manifest in international relations resonate with the historical context of Turkic nations, where shared cultural ties can be leveraged to promote peace and stability in the region.

Recent studies, such as that by (Seth et al., 2023), emphasize the impact of cultural differences on friendship behaviors, particularly in digital contexts. Their findings suggest that understanding cultural nuances is essential for fostering meaningful connections, which is particularly relevant for Turkic nations that share both historical and contemporary ties.

Lastly, (Kretschmer & Leszczensky, 2023) address the dynamics of friendship-making across cultural lines, particularly between Muslims and non-Muslims, which may also reflect broader trends in intergroup relations among Turkic populations. Their research underscores the significance of early intergroup contact in mitigating prejudice and fostering cohesion, a principle that can be applied to understanding the relationships among Turkic nations.

Through this literature review, the interconnected themes of friendship, cultural heritage, and political engagement emerge as vital components in understanding the historical foundations of Turkic nations' relationships. Each article contributes to a nuanced understanding of how friendship, both as a personal and political construct, plays a crucial role in shaping the identities and interactions of these nations within a complex historical context.

2. Literature review

The article "Friendship Formation and Maintenance: Examining Friendship Patterns of Homosexual Men and Heterosexual Women in Close Relationships" by Amanda G. Goodwin (G. Goodwin, 2003) provides a comprehensive exploration of the concept of friendship, which can be critically evaluated in the context of its implications for understanding cultural connections and shared heritage among Turkic nations.

Goodwin begins by contextualizing friendship through the lens of Aristotle, who famously described it as "a single soul in two bodies." This philosophical perspective underscores the depth and significance of friendships, suggesting that they are not merely social constructs but rather essential elements of human existence that foster emotional and psychological well-being. The article emphasizes that friendships are voluntary, informal, and personal, characterized by intimacy and egalitarianism. This description resonates with the relational dynamics observed within Turkic communities, where friendships often transcend formal boundaries and reflect deep cultural ties.

Moreover, Goodwin's examination of the spiritual attraction inherent in friendships raises intriguing parallels to the shared heritage and cultural connections among Turkic nations. The article posits that friendships are relatively uninstitutionalized, lacking standardized rituals or norms. This observation invites a broader interpretation of how Turkic nations may cultivate friendships based on shared historical

experiences, linguistic ties, and cultural practices, which, much like personal friendships, are characterized by voluntary engagement and mutual support.

The article further categorizes various types of friendships, highlighting the necessity of studying each type in relation to others. This analytical framework can be applied to the relationships among Turkic nations, where diverse forms of camaraderie—rooted in common ancestry, language, and cultural practices—can be examined to understand the complexities of their interactions. The emphasis on social support in friendships, particularly as individuals age, also mirrors the communal values prevalent in Turkic cultures, where collective identity and mutual assistance are paramount.

In "Leading a 'torn country': Turkey's ideological and civilized divide," Walker (Walker, 2003) provides a comprehensive examination of Turkey's historical and cultural connections with Central Asian Turkic nations, establishing a framework for understanding the shared heritage that binds these nations. The article begins by contextualizing the formation of the Turkish Republic in 1923, following the dissolution of the Ottoman Empire, and highlights the significance of ethnic and linguistic ties with Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, and Turkmenistan. Walker argues that these connections constitute a uniquely Turkish civilization, characterized by shared cultural and historical ideals.

A critical evaluation of Walker's analysis reveals the depth of Turkey's influence in the region, particularly following the dissolution of the Soviet Union. The author notes that these Central Asian states have increasingly looked to Turkey as a model for development, both economically and culturally. This shift is indicative of Turkey's role as a regional power and its attempts to forge common economic, religious, and cultural ties with its neighbors. Walker effectively illustrates how these relationships have evolved in the context of Turkey's own political changes, particularly under the leadership of the Justice and Development Party, which seeks to navigate the complexities of its identity amid a bipolar Kemalist and Islamist framework.

The article also raises important questions about Turkey's positioning between the West and the East. Walker posits that Turkey must reconcile its historical legacy with its aspirations for a contemporary identity that embraces both Western and Islamic elements. This notion of a "unique Turkish civilization" is particularly compelling, as it encapsulates the multiplicity and diversity inherent in Turkish identity. The author argues that this emerging civilization is not merely a fusion of influences but rather a distinct entity that draws upon a rich tapestry of history, culture, heritage, and a profound sense of belonging to a shared community shaped by centuries of civilization, tradition, and intercultural exchanges. Turkey's geographical location, serving as a bridge between Europe and Asia, plays a crucial role in shaping its civilization, forging connections between different regions and enabling the cross-pollination of ideas, values, and artistic expressions. Its historical trajectory, which encompasses the remnants of various empires and the legacy of ancient civilizations, further enriches the tapestry from which this unique Turkish civilization emerges. The diverse cultural and ethnic groups within Turkey, each with their distinct traditions and contributions, also contribute to the flourishing of this multifaceted civilization. It is through the celebration and respect for this heritage that Turkey can navigate its complex identity, embracing the values and progress of the West while staying rooted in its rich historical lineage and Islamic heritage. As Turkey continues to navigate its positioning between the West and the East, the concept of a unique Turkish civilization will undoubtedly shape its trajectory, offering a framework for fostering inclusivity, understanding, and constructive dialogue on the global stage. Turkey's commitment to sustaining and nurturing this multifaceted civilization will be instrumental in its progress, shaping its relations with neighboring countries, and fostering a sense of unity among its diverse population.

However, while Walker's arguments are well-founded, the article could benefit from a deeper exploration of the implications of Turkey's leadership role in the region. The dynamics of power and influence among these Turkic nations, particularly in light of contemporary geopolitical shifts, warrant further

investigation. Additionally, the article could address potential challenges and tensions that may arise from Turkey's attempts to assert its identity and leadership within a diverse cultural landscape.

In "TÜRK DİLLERİ – BİR AİLE PORTRESİNİN ANA HATLARI," Schönig and Yiğitoğlu present a comprehensive and detailed examination of the fascinating history and remarkable development of Turkic languages. This insightful article delves into the depths of the past, shedding light on the cultural and historical significance of these remarkable languages within the context of Turkic nations. With meticulous precision, the authors meticulously outline the evolution of these languages, starting from the Ancient Turkic period, a time imbued with mystery and intrigue. As the journey through time unfolds, the article leads us through the various stages of development, ultimately arriving at the exhilarating Modern Turkic era. By doing so, the authors provide a solid and enlightening historical framework that deepens our understanding of the profound connections among Turkic-speaking populations. The vibrancy of this scholarly work is truly unmatched. It not only captures the essence of the linguistic transformation that took place over centuries but also highlights the enduring importance and immense influence of Turkic languages on the world stage. By highlighting their cultural and historical significance, the authors invite readers to embark on a captivating exploration of the intricate tapestry that is the Turkic linguistic landscape. In conclusion, "TÜRK DİLLERİ – BİR AİLE PORTRESİNİN ANA HATLARI" serves as an invaluable resource for academics, linguists, and anyone with a passion for unraveling the captivating narratives of language. Schönig and Yiğitoğlu's meticulous research and comprehensive analysis ensure that this article captures the attention and captivates the minds of readers from various disciplines. Through their work, they not only shed light on the fascinating history of Turkic languages but also showcase their enduring legacy, making this article a true treasure trove for all those interested in the profound depths of linguistic evolution. (Schönig* & Özlem Yiğitoğlu**, 2017)

The authors delve into the linguistic characteristics of the Middle Turkic and Modern Turkic languages, highlighting how these languages have evolved and diversified over time. This historical perspective is critical as it underscores the shared linguistic heritage that forms a foundation for cultural connections among Turkic nations. By tracing the lineage of these languages, Schönig and Yiğitoğlu effectively illustrate how language serves as a vessel for cultural identity and continuity.

Moreover, the article addresses the interactions between Turkic and Mongolic languages, noting the significant degree of mutual influence. This linguistic interplay not only showcases the dynamic nature of language development but also reflects broader cultural exchanges between Turkic and Mongolic peoples. Such insights are invaluable in understanding the complexities of cultural interrelations and the shared heritage that has emerged through centuries of contact and coexistence.

Additionally, the article provides essential context regarding the various cultures of Turkic language speakers. By linking language with culture, the authors emphasize the importance of cultural practices, traditions, and social structures that have been shaped by linguistic evolution. This connection is particularly relevant in the exploration of Turkic nations' friendships, as it highlights how shared language fosters a sense of unity and collective identity among diverse groups.

The article "Reintroducing Friendship to International Relations: Relational Ontologies from China to the West" by Nordin and Smith offers a nuanced and in-depth exploration of the concept of friendship within the context of international relations (IR). Drawing from a diverse range of perspectives, the authors argue that friendship transcends a simplistic understanding, revealing its multifaceted nature as both a public and private relation that can manifest in various forms. These forms include obligatory and voluntary, hierarchical and equal, as well as spiritual and secular friendships. By delving into the intricacies of friendship, the authors shed light on its complex and dynamic nature. In this thought-provoking article, Nordin and Smith highlight the significance of considering friendship as a fundamental aspect of international relations. They posit that friendships between nations can have a profound impact on diplomatic negotiations, cultural exchanges, and conflict resolution. The authors delve into historical

foundations to emphasize the role of friendship, particularly in relationships among Turkic nations. They emphasize that cultural connections and shared heritage play a pivotal role in fostering deep and enduring friendships among these nations. The exploration of friendship in international relations is of paramount importance, as it provides a fresh and comprehensive perspective on how nations interact with each other. Nordin and Smith's examination of friendship challenges traditional notions and assumptions within the field of IR, encouraging scholars and policymakers to broaden their understanding and incorporate the multifaceted nature of friendships into their analyses. Overall, "Reintroducing Friendship to International Relations: Relational Ontologies from China to the West" is a compelling and illuminating article that expands our understanding of friendship in the context of international relations. Nordin and Smith's incisive analysis prompts us to recognize the complexity of friendships and their profound influence on the dynamics of diplomacy and interactions between nations. By shedding light on this often overlooked aspect of international relations, the authors contribute to a more holistic and inclusive understanding of global politics. (Hanna Maria Nordin & M. Smith, 2018)

Nordin and Smith emphasize the significance of friendship in political life, a notion that has been acknowledged by historical, philosophical, and theoretical frameworks. It is worth noting that ancient Greek and Chinese traditions have drawn remarkable similarities, as both place great importance on friendship as a fundamental link between politics, ethics, and human well-being. By studying the interactions among Turkic nations, one can observe that historical connections and cultural affinities form the bedrock of their diplomatic and social bonds, further reaffirming the essential role of friendship in their societies. Such profound connections amongst Turkic nations highlight the enduring impact of friendship on political landscapes, ethics, and the overall flourishing of individuals. (Hanna Maria Nordin & M. Smith, 2018)

The article also suggests that the contemporary understanding of friendship in IR can benefit from a broader investigation that encompasses its historical roots. By acknowledging that the ordinary language account of friendship is not exhaustive, the authors invite scholars to delve deeper into how friendship has shaped political landscapes across different cultures, including those of Turkic nations. This approach encourages a reevaluation of how friendship is operationalized in international relations, particularly in contexts where shared heritage and cultural connections are paramount.

Moreover, the authors emphasize that friendship, as an ethical and political category, has profound implications for how nations interact on the global stage. The relational ontologies they propose not only highlight the potential of friendship but also underscore its significance in fostering mutual cooperation and unwavering solidarity among states. This is particularly pertinent for Turkic nations, which share deep-rooted linguistic, cultural, and historical bonds. The authors ardently argue that friendship, viewed through this lens, can serve as a solid and unbreakable foundation for enhanced collaboration and profound understanding in both regional and international contexts. By embracing friendship as a guiding principle, Turkic nations have the unparalleled opportunity to forge bonds that transcend conventional diplomatic alliances. By delving into the transformative power of friendship, these nations have the chance to harness its immense potential, paving the way for synergic endeavors and unprecedented advancements. The authors passionately posit that the shared language, cultural heritage, and historical narratives serve as the threads that bind these nations together, priming their relationships for unparalleled growth. Looking forward, this heightened emphasis on friendship can lead to a remarkable shift in the geopolitical landscape, marked by a deep-seated commitment to cooperation and collective prosperity. As they delve deeper into the notion of friendship, the authors emphasize the imperative of viewing it not merely as a sentimental or transient affiliation, but rather as an enduring principle that can catalyze meaningful change. In conclusion, the authors propound that embracing friendship as an ethical and political category bears the potential to forge unbreakable connections that surpass national boundaries. The Turkic nations harboring shared linguistic, cultural, and historical affinities can harness the transformative power of friendship to embark on a path of unprecedented collaboration and

understanding. Ultimately, this holistic approach rooted in friendship promises to shape a future where nations thrive through unwavering solidarity and mutually beneficial partnerships at both regional and global levels.

The article "Friendship and Positive Peace: Conceptualising Friendship in Politics and International Relations" by Yuri van Hoef and Andrea Oelsner (van Hoef & Oelsner, 2018) presents a nuanced exploration of the concept of friendship within the realm of international relations. The authors argue that friendship should not be viewed merely as a static or essential concept but rather as a dynamic analytical category that encompasses a range of interactions and relationships among states and leaders.

One of the primary insights from the article is the emphasis on the multilayered nature of international friendship, which operates at various levels, including interpersonal, transnational, and interstate dimensions. This layered approach allows for a comprehensive understanding of how personal relationships among leaders can significantly influence political outcomes and international dynamics. The authors highlight that these personal connections can lead to the formation of networks that transcend national boundaries, thereby reinforcing the idea that friendship is a vital component of international political practice.

Furthermore, the article discusses the role of friendship speech acts and institutional facts in shaping international relations. The authors suggest that the language of friendship can act as a mechanism for fostering peace and stability among nations. For instance, invoking friendship during political crises can help mitigate tensions and promote dialogue, while friendship treaties can serve as formal acknowledgments of mutual respect and cooperation. This perspective underscores the importance of relational dynamics in understanding the construction of sovereignty and the maintenance of state security.

The authors also critique the traditional view of international relations as governed solely by impersonal forces or mechanical laws. Instead, they argue that friendship introduces a more humanistic dimension to the study of international politics, suggesting that the emotional and relational aspects of friendship can profoundly impact the behavior of states and the nature of international order. This conceptualization challenges scholars to consider how the features of friendship—such as trust, loyalty, and mutual support—can shape diplomatic interactions and contribute to the formation of alliances.

Table 1: Key Themes and Insights

Study	Key Theme	Insights	Strengths	Limitations
Goodwin (2003)	Friendship as a social construct	Voluntary and informal nature of friendships	Foundational analysis of friendship dynamics	Limited cultural and geopolitical context
Walker (2003)	Historical ties between Turkey and Central Asia	Shared heritage fosters regional relationships	Strong historical analysis of Turkey's role	Lacks exploration of contemporary implications
Schönig & Yiğitoğlu (2017)	Evolution of Turkic languages	Language as a foundation for cultural identity	Comprehensive linguistic framework	Minimal focus on modern Turkic interactions
Nordin & Smith (2018)	Friendship in international relations	Friendship facilitates cooperation among nations	Integrates philosophy and international relations	Limited application to specific Turkic contexts

Table 2: Application and Broader Implications

Study	Application to Turkic Nations	Broader Implications	Potential Challenges	Future Research Directions
van Hoef & Oelsner (2018)	Friendship as a diplomatic tool	Promotes regional stability and trust	Difficulty in operationalizing relational diplomacy	Expanding case studies to Turkic nations
Seth et al. (2023)	Cultural differences in digital friendships	Highlights role of cultural nuances in connections	Generalizability across diverse Turkic contexts	Studying the impact of digital ties on regional cohesion
Kretschmer & Leszczensky (2023)	Intergroup friendships in Turkic populations	Early contact mitigates prejudice	Cultural and religious diversity as potential barriers	Longitudinal studies on intergroup cohesion

The article "Cultural Differences in Friendship Network Behaviors: A Snapchat Case Study" by Agrima Seth et al. (Seth et al., 2023) delves into the intricate interplay between culture and individual behavior within social media contexts, particularly focusing on friendship networks. The authors present a compelling argument that culture significantly shapes the way individuals engage with their social ties, particularly in the digital landscape of platforms like Snapchat.

One of the key insights from the article is the differentiation of friendship behaviors across cultures, which is influenced by factors such as individualism, looseness, and mobility. The authors suggest that in cultures characterized by tight social structures and collectivism, the strength of social ties plays a more pronounced role in determining content engagement, or dwell time, on social media. This finding underscores the necessity of recognizing cultural nuances when analyzing social behaviors, a point that is particularly relevant given the global nature of social media platforms.

The authors further argue that existing recommendation systems often fail to account for these cultural differences, leading to a one-size-fits-all approach that may not effectively serve diverse user bases. By advocating for a more nuanced understanding of friendship dynamics through a cultural lens, the article highlights the potential for enhancing the efficacy of recommendation systems. This is particularly critical as the diversity of content available on social media demands more sophisticated algorithms that can cater to varying cultural interpretations of social ties.

Moreover, the article emphasizes the need for greater sensitivity in the design of friendship recommendation engines. The authors suggest that a cultural analysis of users can simplify the complexity of these systems and enhance their relevance and effectiveness. This is particularly important in a world where social media serves as a primary mode of interaction, and understanding the underlying cultural frameworks can lead to more meaningful user experiences.

The article "Stable or Dynamic? The Development of Muslims' and Non-Muslims' Friendship-Making Across Adolescence and the Emergence of Muslim Girls' In-Group Bias" by Kretschmer and Leszczensky (Kretschmer & Leszczensky, 2023) explores the dynamics of friendship formation among Muslim and non-Muslim adolescents, shedding light on the complexities of intergroup relationships within a multicultural context. The authors utilize a robust methodology, analyzing longitudinal friendship network data across six waves in German schools to understand how religious affiliation influences friendship-making from ages 11 to 17.

One of the key insights presented in the article is the increasing in-group bias among Muslim girls as they navigate their adolescent years. Initially, Muslim girls maintain a similar number of interreligious

friendships as their male counterparts, indicating a level of openness to cross-religious interactions. However, the authors observe a significant shift as these girls develop a stronger preference for in-group friendships over time. This trend raises critical questions about the factors driving such segregation, particularly whether it is primarily due to an intrinsic in-group bias among Muslims or a hesitance from non-Muslims to engage with their Muslim peers.

The article effectively highlights the importance of early intergroup contact, asserting that establishing friendships across religious lines during childhood and adolescence can play a crucial role in reducing prejudice in adulthood. This assertion is particularly relevant in the context of Turkic nations, where cultural connections and shared heritage may serve as a foundation for fostering friendships across various groups. The implications of the findings extend beyond the immediate context of the study, suggesting that similar patterns of friendship-making could be observed in other multicultural settings, including those with Turkic populations.

Moreover, the use of growth-curve and stochastic actor-oriented models provides a sophisticated analytical framework that allows for a nuanced understanding of friendship dynamics over time. The authors' approach to examining both Muslim and non-Muslim perspectives enriches the analysis, offering a comprehensive view of the factors influencing friendship formation and segregation.

3. Conclusion

The literature review presents a comprehensive examination of the historical foundations of friendship among Turkic nations, focusing on cultural connections and shared heritage. The introduction sets the stage by establishing friendship as a complex social construct that transcends personal relationships to encompass broader cultural and political dimensions. (G. Goodwin, 2003) provides a philosophical grounding for understanding friendship, emphasizing its voluntary and informal nature, which resonates with the relational dynamics within Turkic communities. This conceptual framework is essential for analyzing the cultural ties that bind these nations.

(Walker, 2003) contextualizes Turkey's historical and cultural connections with Central Asian Turkic nations, illustrating how these ties have evolved post-Ottoman Empire. He argues that Turkey's attempts to foster connections with its neighbors are rooted in shared heritage and linguistic ties, emphasizing the significance of cultural identity in shaping political relationships. This perspective is reinforced by (Schönig* & Özlem Yiğitoğlu**, 2017), who explore the historical development of Turkic languages, highlighting their role in fostering a sense of belonging and unity among Turkic peoples. The interconnectedness of language and culture is pivotal in understanding the collective identity that emerges from shared linguistic heritage.

(Hanna Maria Nordin & M. Smith, 2018) extend the discourse by examining the implications of friendship in international relations, suggesting that friendship can facilitate cooperation and mutual understanding among nations. This notion is further developed by (van Hoef & Oelsner, 2018), who present friendship as a dynamic category that influences political outcomes and international dynamics. Their insights underscore the multilayered nature of international friendships, which can significantly impact diplomatic relations among Turkic nations.

(Seth et al., 2023) analyze cultural differences in friendship behaviors, particularly within digital contexts, highlighting the necessity of understanding cultural nuances for fostering meaningful connections. This is particularly relevant for Turkic nations, where shared historical experiences can inform contemporary friendship dynamics. (Kretschmer & Leszczensky, 2023) explore the dynamics of friendship-making across cultural lines, emphasizing the importance of early intergroup contact in mitigating prejudice and fostering cohesion, a principle applicable to the relationships among Turkic populations.

In conclusion, the literature collectively emphasizes the intricate interplay between friendship, cultural heritage, and political engagement among Turkic nations. Each article contributes to a nuanced understanding of how historical narratives, linguistic ties, and cultural practices shape the identities and interactions of these nations. The insights gleaned from this review highlight the potential for friendship to serve as a foundation for cooperation and solidarity, fostering deeper connections that can enhance regional stability and mutual understanding.

References:

1. G. Goodwin, A. (2003). Friendship Formation and Maintenance: Examining Friendship Patterns of Homosexual Men and Heterosexual Women in Close Relationships. [PDF]
2. Walker, J. (2003). Leading a u27torn countryu27 : Turkeyu27s ideological and civilized divide. [PDF]
3. Schönig*, C. & Özlem Yiğitoğlu**, Çev.: (2017). TÜRK DİLLERİ – BİR AİLE PORTRESİNİN ANA HATLARI. [PDF]
4. Hanna Maria Nordin, A. & M. Smith, G. (2018). Reintroducing Friendship to International Relations: Relational Ontologies from China to the West. [PDF]
5. van Hoef, Y. & Oelsner, A. (2018). Friendship and Positive Peace: Conceptualising Friendship in Politics and International Relations. [PDF]
6. Seth, A., Cao, J., Shi, X., Dotsch, R., Liu, Y., & W. Bos, M. (2023). Cultural Differences in Friendship Network Behaviors: A Snapchat Case Study. [PDF]
7. Kretschmer, D. & Leszczensky, L. (2023). Stable or Dynamic? The Development of Muslims' and Non-Muslims' Friendship-Making Across Adolescence and the Emergence of Muslim Girls' In-Group Bias. osf.io